

Machine Learning Model Transferability for Urban Point Cloud Classification: A Study of Random Forest and XGBoost across Datasets

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Abstract— The increasing availability of point cloud data from platforms such as Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) has facilitated urban mapping and analysis. However, the transferability of machine learning models trained on different point cloud datasets remains an open challenge. This study evaluates the transferability of two random forest and XGBoost, for urban point cloud classification across different datasets. Two datasets were used, a photogrammetry and a LiDAR dataset. The LiDAR dataset was used for training and the photogrammetry to assess model transferability. XGBoost outperformed random forest in both benchmark and unseen photogrammetric datasets, with facades and roofs showing the best transferability. The study highlights the need for larger annotated datasets and improved model generalization for robust urban point cloud classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Urban centers and cities are characterized by their complexity and constant evolution, driven by human activity. Mapping these environments is essential for various applications, such as flood modeling (Zamboni et al., 2024). Point clouds play a pivotal role in understanding urban environments, serving as a valuable tool for detecting, delineating, and mitigating issues associated with urbanization (Stilla and Xu, 2023). The increasing accessibility of data collection platforms, such as Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), has led to a significant reduction in the cost and time required for acquiring raw point cloud data. However, to generate meaningful data, it is essential to incorporate semantic information into the raw point cloud.

Machine learning has been extensively employed in a range of data processing tasks. In the context of 3D point cloud semantic

segmentation, supervised machine learning and deep learning approaches have garnered significant attention. Within a vast array of models, decision tree-based methods, such as random forest and XGBoost, have demonstrated competitive performance in comparison to deep learning approaches for urban point cloud segmentation (e.g. Kölle et al., 2021), while exhibiting a comparatively uncomplicated structure and reduced computational demands. However, the scarcity of large-scale labeled datasets has posed a significant challenge in the adoption of supervised machine learning methods.

Compared to image annotations, 3D labelling is more difficult and demanding. Thus, benchmark point cloud datasets usually cover only small areas. Moreover, across available open datasets, there is a high discrepancy between hand annotated classes. This discrepancy can render such datasets domain-specific, thereby limiting the generalizability of models trained on these datasets.

The objective of this study is to assess the transferability of random forest and XGBoost machine learning models across diverse datasets. We trained both machine learning models using the H3D benchmark dataset (Kölle et al., 2021). Subsequently, the performance of these models on the semantic segmentation task in a novel and unseen test dataset was assessed.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Study area and photogrammetry dataset

We conducted UAV flights in a small urban area in the southern region of Germany using a DJI Matrice 300RTK with a P1 full-frame camera (35 mm focal length and 4.4 μm pixel pitch).

The flight height was set at 120 meters, which resulted in a ground sampling distance (GSD) of 1.47 centimeters. A total of 341 images were collected, with a side and forward overlap of 70%. The generation of the photogrammetry point cloud was achieved through the implementation of Structure from Motion and Multi-View Stereo techniques. The generation of the point cloud was facilitated by the utilization of nine ground control points (GCP) and twelve permanent structures (e.g., manholes) that served as checkpoints (CP), yielding a root mean square error (RMSE) of 2 cm. A segment of the comprehensive point cloud was manually labeled encompassing about 30 million points (about 31% of the total number of points). For the labelling, we considered the same classes as in the H3D dataset (Kölle et al., 2021), except for the chimney class. Hereinafter referred to as a photogrammetry dataset.

B. H3D benchmark dataset

The H3D dataset was proposed by Kölle et al. (2021). The data was collected using an UAV equipped with LiDAR, in conjunction with two oblique-looking cameras. The flight height was set at 50 meters, which resulted in a GSD of 1.5 to 3 centimeters. The resulting dataset offers a high-dense point cloud, with 800 points per square meter. In addition to the XYZ coordinates, the dataset encompasses LiDAR features, including echo number and reflectance. Additionally, the RGB color information was made available. The March 2019 Epoch was selected for analysis due to its comprehensive coverage of the area and the capture of data under close-to-optimal flight conditions. The dataset contains eleven classes: low vegetation, impervious surface, vehicle, urban furniture, roof, facade, shrub, tree, soil/gravel, vertical surface, and chimney. Different from the photogrammetry dataset, the H3D dataset was captured with a LiDAR, therefore, presenting different intrinsic characteristics. We selected a subset of points from the train and validation sets of the March 2019 epoch of the H3D dataset. A random grid subsampling technique was employed to extract a subset of points from the original, high-density point cloud. The train set was divided into two subsets: one used for model training and the other to assess the training performance. The validation set from the H3D dataset was utilized to evaluate the models.

C. Random forest and XGBoost

Random forest and XGBoost are tree based ensemble machine learning algorithms. However, they present key architecture differences. Random forest employs a bagging technique, where individual trees are trained in parallel, using a subset of the training dataset. This method takes the prediction of each tree and based on the majority vote of predictions, makes the final predictions. On the other hand, XGBoost applies a boosting technique, where trees are built sequentially to correct errors of previous trees. It builds multiple decision trees sequentially, correcting errors at each step to improve accuracy while

incorporating regularization to prevent overfitting. The number of trees and their depth are key hyperparameters for both Random Forest and XGBoost, directly affecting model complexity and performance. Number of trees controls how many decision trees are used, while depth determines how many splits each tree can make, influencing how well the model captures patterns or overfits.

D. Experimental setup

The training of classification models was achieved through the integration of geometric and radiometric features. The geometric features of all points in the train and validation sets from the benchmark dataset, as well as the photogrammetry dataset, were computed in accordance with the methodology proposed by Weinmann et al. (2015) and Chehata et al. (2009). A multi-search radius approach was employed to analyze features at various levels. The search radius was set to 0.125, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 2, 3, and 5 meters, and spherical neighborhoods were utilized. For each search radius, the following metrics were calculated: the sum of eigenvalues, omni-variance, eigen-entropy, anisotropy, planarity, linearity, surface variation, sphericity, verticality, the first and second largest eigenvalues from the principal component analysis (PCA), and the number of neighbors. In addition, point density and height above ground were incorporated as geometric features. In addition, radiometric characteristics were taken into account, with the calculated HSV (hue, saturation, value) colors being utilized in conjunction with RGB (red, green, blue) values. Subsequent to the initial testing phase, the number of trees was set to 18 and tree depth to 100 for the random forest model. In the context of XGBoost, a configuration of 25 trees with a depth of 100 was implemented.

E. Evaluation metrics

To evaluate and compare different models across different datasets, the weighted precision, recall, and F1-score are assessed. Precision is defined as the accuracy of positive predictions made by the model. Precision is calculated as the ratio of true positives to the sum of true positives and false positives. Values close to 1 indicate that most positive predictions were accurate, i.e., almost no wrong predictions were made. Recall, on the other hand, signifies the proportion of all positive values that were accurately classified as positive, and it is defined as the ratio of true positives and the sum of true positives and false negatives. Values approaching 1 suggest that most actual positive cases were identified, i.e., not many were missing. The F1-score is a harmonic mean between precision and recall, synthesizing both into a single value. Due to the high imbalance present in the dataset, a weighted strategy was employed to calculate all metrics. Weights were calculated based on the proportion of each class on the dataset. Furthermore, a confusion matrix was utilized to assess the performance of each model across various classes.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Model performance on the H3D dataset

The random forest model demonstrated an average weighted precision of 0.83, a recall of 0.844, and an F1-score of 0.833 on the validation set. In comparison, XGBoost demonstrated a marginally superior overall performance, with an average precision of 0.836, a recall of 0.850, and an F1-score of 0.841.

Figure 1. Confusion matrix (normalized by column) for the random forest model on the H3D dataset.

Figure 2. Confusion matrix (normalized by column) for the XGBoost model on the H3D dataset.

As demonstrated in Figures 1 and 2, XGBoost exhibited superior performance across all classes, with a notable decline in performance for classes with a smaller number of points, such as vehicle and vertical surface. For classes with more representative features, such as roof and facade, both models demonstrated comparable performance. Additionally, the XGBoost model exhibited slightly higher performance in vegetation classes.

B. Model transferability assessment

In this study, trained machine learning models were utilized to generate semantic segmentation for each point also on the photogrammetry dataset. The XGBoost model demonstrated a marginal superiority over the random forest model in terms of the photogrammetry dataset's F1-score, which was recorded at 0.60. In contrast, the random forest model attained an F1-score of 0.55

for the same evaluation metric. As demonstrated in Tables 1 and 2, both models generally exhibited comparable precision and recall values.

It was observed that XGBoost exhibited superior precision for classes with a greater number of points and a higher recall for classes with a smaller number of points. In terms of precision, XGBoost demonstrated a substantial enhancement, with an increase in precision values of approximately 0.1 for classes designated as impervious surface and tree. A similar increase in recall values was observed for classes vehicles and urban furniture. This behavior might indicate that XGBoost can better handle an imbalanced dataset, giving more weight to minority classes, with the gradient boosting technique adjusting weights iteratively.

TABLE I. PRECISION, RECALL, F1-SCORE, AND NUMBER OF POINTS OF EACH CLASS OF THE PHOTOGRAMMETRY DATASET USING THE RANDOM FOREST MODEL.

Class	Metrics			
	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Number of points
Low vegetation	0.80	0.49	0.61	5291449
Impervious surface	0.41	0.61	0.49	1226356
Vehicle	0.29	0.36	0.32	87539
Urban furniture	0.01	0.48	0.02	27577
Roof	0.71	0.91	0.79	819837
Facade	0.66	0.75	0.71	897068
Shrub	0.09	0.42	0.15	336267
Tree	0.70	0.45	0.54	1570103
Soil-Gravel	0.06	0.01	0.01	604228
Vertical Surface	0.23	0.06	0.10	89717
Weighted average	0.65	0.52	0.55	10950141

TABLE II. PRECISION, RECALL, F1-SCORE, AND NUMBER OF POINTS OF EACH CLASS OF THE PHOTOGRAMMETRY DATASET USING THE XGBOOST MODEL

Class	Metrics			
	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Number of points
Low vegetation	0.81	0.55	0.66	5291449
Impervious surface	0.53	0.64	0.58	1226356
Vehicle	0.26	0.46	0.33	87539
Urban furniture	0.01	0.59	0.02	27577
Roof	0.68	0.94	0.79	819837
Facade	0.72	0.81	0.76	897068

Class	Metrics			
	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Number of points
Shrub	0.12	0.36	0.18	336267
Tree	0.81	0.48	0.60	1570103
Soil-Gravel	0.08	0.02	0.03	604228
Vertical Surface	0.24	0.10	0.14	89717
Weighted average	0.69	0.56	0.60	10950141

As illustrated in Figures 3 and 4, the confusion matrix for both models on the photogrammetry dataset is presented. It is evident that XGBoost demonstrated a superior overall performance. Roof and facades exhibited higher degrees of transferability among the classes. This observation may be indicative of a certain degree of similarity between the classes across the two datasets, given their common origin in urban environments within Germany. The class of vertical surfaces, which exhibited the lowest score, was found to be highly misclassified as urban furniture and facades. The misclassification of these three classes, which share similar geometric characteristics, is likely the primary cause of the observed discrepancies. The soil-gravel class exhibited the poorest performance across both datasets, demonstrating a high degree of misclassification as low vegetation.

Figure 3. Confusion matrix (normalized by row) for the random forest model on the photogrammetry dataset dataset.

Figure 4. Confusion matrix (normalized by row) for the XGBoost model on the photogrammetry dataset dataset.

IV. CONCLUSION

The XGBoost model demonstrated a marginal superiority in its performance on the laser scanning benchmark dataset, and exhibiting enhanced transferability to the unseen, photogrammetric dataset. Among all ten classes, facades and roof demonstrated the highest performance across both datasets, while soil-gravel exhibited the lowest performance. The findings of this study demonstrate the capacity of machine learning models to generate satisfactory outcomes on unseen, cross-platform data; nevertheless, their implementation necessitates meticulous consideration. Our findings underscore the necessity of enhancing the accessibility of large-scale annotated point cloud datasets, increasing data variability, and facilitating the development of models with a higher degree of generalization.

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